

COMBINED METHODS FOR THE TREATMENT OF PULPITIS IN ELDERLY INDIVIDUALS**Aliyev Agil Nariman***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor***Alizada Aysel Rafiq****Gurbanov Ramin Yagub***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant**Department of Therapeutic Dentistry Assistant**Azerbaijan Medical University,**Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

To identify age-related characteristics of the clinical course of various forms of pulpitis and to evaluate the effectiveness of its treatment using combined methods in elderly and senile individuals.

Keywords: elderly age, pulpitis, caries, fluoride, root canal.

One of the important areas in the development of gerontology and dentistry is the emerging scientific field of **gerostomatology**. With the increasing proportion of elderly individuals in the populations of most developed countries, their number is also growing among dental patients.

The treatment of pulp inflammation holds a significant place in modern dentistry. Patients with pulpitis make up **14-20% or more** of all dental patients. Among the various methods of pulpitis treatment, **the biological method** deserves special attention, as it allows for the preservation of pulp vitality in reversible forms of the disease. However, the **limited application** of pulp vitality preservation methods is due to the insufficient proficiency of many dentists in this technique, as well as the difficulty of **timely diagnosis** of the early stages of pulp inflammation due to the rapid progression of degenerative processes.

In recent years, research efforts have been focused on **improving early and differential diagnostics** of reversible pulpitis and developing new **drugs and therapeutic compositions** for the pathogenetic treatment of pulp inflammation. Advanced diagnostic methods, such as **laser Doppler flowmetry, autoradiography using cell markers with reduced oxygen tension, and biochemical techniques**, have highlighted the **crucial role of microcirculatory disorders and cellular hypoxia** in the pathogenesis of pulpitis.

Based on the latest scientific insights into the **etiopathogenetic aspects of pulpitis**, both domestic and international researchers have proposed a range of **pharmacological agents** aimed at correcting inflammatory changes in the dental pulp and stimulating **reparative processes** within it.

Study Objective

To identify age-related features of the clinical course of various forms of pulpitis and evaluate the effectiveness of its treatment using combined methods in elderly and senile individuals.

Materials and Methods

A total of 324 patients with various forms of pulpitis, aged 45 to 65 years, were observed. Of these, only 11 were practically healthy. All others suffered from various cardiovascular diseases in the compensation stage. Including individuals with such pathology in the study group was a necessary measure. People over 45

years old are typically burdened with a wide range of diseases, which naturally affect the results of pulpitis treatment. Therefore, a group with comparable overall pathology was selected. In addition to pulpitis, oral conditions allowed for a maximum of 2-3 filled decayed teeth and prostheses replacing 1-2 missing teeth.

Research Results

As our observations show, the composition of the therapeutic paste has a significant impact. Thus, with the conservative method using zinc oxide-eugenol paste, the positive result in the short term was $85.71 \pm 4.7\%$, in the long term – $90.91 \pm 4.09\%$, and $97.10 \pm 2.02\%$.

The nature of complications in both groups was similar; the differences were in the frequency of their occurrence. Complications were observed more frequently between 2 days and 1 month in the form of residual pulpitis (immediate observations) in $6.67 \pm 4.47\%$ of the control group and in $5.19 \pm 2.42\%$ of the group treated with mafenide acetate, or were related to filling defects (short-term observations) – $4.28 \pm 6.72\%$ and $4.1 \pm 2.22\%$, respectively. In all groups, the results were statistically significant.

An analysis of complications conducted at later stages showed that they manifested as chronic periodontitis or its exacerbation: in $16.67 \pm 9.21\%$ of the control group and $4.29 \pm 2.32\%$ in the mafenide acetate group.

According to our observations, the results of treating acute pulpitis with the conservative method and vital amputation are related to the overall health condition of the patient and the method of impact on the pulp. In the groups using zinc oxide-eugenol paste, positive results were achieved in $62.5 \pm 5.38\%$ of patients with the conservative method, $70 \pm 5.53\%$ with vital amputation, and $79.5 \pm 4.02\%$ and $86.98 \pm 3.69\%$, respectively, with the therapeutic complex.

Conclusions

1. The analysis of the prevalence, frequency, and structure of pulpitis morbidity in different age groups revealed a dependence of the incidence of various forms of acute and chronic pulpitis on the age of patients.

2. Although chronic forms of pulpitis predominated in all age groups, the frequency of acute pulpitis

sharply decreased with age: in elderly and senile patients, chronic forms of pulpitis occurred 4.5-5 times more often than acute forms, and exacerbations of chronic pulpitis were also more frequently observed in elderly individuals.

3. Short-term and long-term monitoring of the health status of young, middle-aged, elderly, and senile patients receiving treatment for various forms of pulpitis using conventional methods and impulse lasers showed that laser therapy provides a stable positive effect, manifested in a significant reduction in the frequency of complications and relapses of the disease.

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